

US COVID19 DATA & FORECAST June 5th, 2020

USA COVID19 DATA & FORECAST June 5th, 2020

● New

● Verhulst forecast of new cases

USA COVID19 DATA & FORECAST June 5th, 2020

—●— New deaths ● Verhulst forecast of decrease of new deaths